

insertion of insect stylets into the feeding sites and indicate that mechanical barriers were not involved in varietal resistance.

Host range studies involving 56 plant species indicated that *N. virescens* can survive and breed only on rice, while *N. nigropictus* has a host range that includes rice, sugarcane, and five graminaceous weeds. *N. nigropictus* showed greater preference for *Leersia hexandra* than for any other plant including TN1 rice. However, both species could lay eggs even on nonhosts. *N. virescens* made more feeding marks and excreted less honeydew when caged on the host plants suited to *N. nigropictus*, suggest-

ing that narrow host specificity may be due to an imbalance in phagostimulants or the presence of phagodeterrents.

These results show that chemosensory, particularly gustatory, stimuli play an important role in host selection in green leafhoppers.

The biochemical causes of resistance to leafhoppers in rice were also investigated. The total phenol content of resistant varieties was relatively higher than that of the susceptible TN1, but it was also high in *L. hexandra*. Thus, individual phenolic compounds may play a role in susceptibility or resistance.

The role of amino acids was not clear because their concentration was low

both in resistant rice varieties and in *L. hexandra*, which was the most suitable host for *N. nigropictus*.

Feeding stimulation and inhibition by various chemicals and plant extracts of resistant and susceptible varieties were bioassayed. Sucrose was highly stimulatory and a few amino acids slightly stimulated feeding. Amino acid derivatives, organic acids, and phenolic compounds were strongly deterrent. Similarly, both GLH species had low preference for chloroform and acetone extracts of resistant varieties, but similar extracts from susceptible plants were readily accepted. ■

Varietal resistance of rice to leaf folder

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A trial was conducted through the upland rice varietal screening program to select varieties suitable for dryland paddy cultivation in the hilly zone of Karnataka in 1980 kharif. Twenty-one entries were included in this trial, replicated three times. During the trial, incidence of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* was severe, but some varieties were observed to have lower levels of damage. The damage on different varieties was recorded (see table). ARC25, KMP133, and KMP58 had minimum damage and were also moderately resistant to blast. ■

Extent of damage^a by leaf folder in different rice varieties. Karnataka, India.

Entry	Leaf damage (%)
Kala keni	69.4
CR222-MW-10	65.5
ARC25	10.6
Black Gora	69.0
Bala	100.0
IR6115-1-1-1	100.0
OR165-85-12	66.9
KMP39	47.2
KMP(A) 57	75.0
OR165-28-14B	51.2
OR165-18-8	100.0
CRM13-3241	100.0
N22	42.4
MR262	75.0
CR143-2-2	100.0
CR245-1	100.0
KMP58	28.7
IET1444	96.7
KMP133	11.8
KMP134	39.4
Jaya	71.8

^aAv of 3 replications.

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Selection pathways for dryland rice breeding

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Progenies of two rice crosses — IR3135 (IR1539-823-1-4/IR1917-3-17) and

IR3189 (IR1721-11-13-20-1-2/C4-63) — were grown and selected under wetland and dryland conditions. The result was three different selection pathways. The pathways (F₂ and F₃) were: 1 = dryland/dryland; 2 = wetland/dryland; and 3 = wetland/wetland lines. F₄ from the two crosses and three pathways were compared under dryland conditions for grain yield and yield components.

The pathways affected neither the grain yield nor the yield components. The two crosses differed significantly in 100-grain weight, tiller number, and plant height, but did not differ significantly in grain yield, panicle number, or panicle length. The variables studied showed no significant interactions.

Statistically nonsignificant mean squares and relatively small variance